

THE ROLE OF GAME EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Game as a method of teaching, transferring social experience, has been used since antiquity. In a modern school, game activities are used by teachers:

- as an independent technology for mastering a concept, topic and even a section of a subject;
- as an element of a more general technology;
- as a lesson or part of it (introduction, control);
- as a technology of extracurricular work.

G.K. Selevko gives the following definition of gaming technology - "this is a type of activity in situations aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-management of behavior develops and improves" [3, p. 256].

The concept of "game pedagogical technologies" includes a fairly extensive group of methods and techniques for organizing the pedagogical process in the form of various pedagogical games. Unlike games in general, pedagogical game has an

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to game educational technologies and their application in foreign language lessons. The functions and value of game forms of teaching in the teaching and educational process in the English language are revealed. Particular attention is paid to the classification of language and speech games. Based on the analysis of existing classifications, the authors propose their own classification, focusing on creative and role-playing games in foreign language lessons.

essential feature - a clearly defined goal of teaching and the corresponding pedagogical result, which can be substantiated, singled out in an explicit form and are characterized by an educational and cognitive orientation [2, p. 140-146].

The place and role of game technology in the educational process, the combination of elements of game and learning largely depend on the teacher's understanding of the functions of pedagogical games. Of particular note are the following:

1. Entertaining: the game is strategically - only an organized cultural space for the child's entertainment, in which he goes from entertainment to development.

2. Communicative: game is a communicative activity that allows the child to enter the real context of the most complex human communications.

3. Self-realization of the child in the game: the game allows, on the one hand, to build and test a project for the removal of specific life difficulties in the child's practice, on the other - to identify the shortcomings of the experience.

4. Therapeutic: game is used as a means of overcoming various difficulties that students have in the course of communication or learning.

5. Diagnostic: the game provides an opportunity for the teacher to diagnose various manifestations of the student (intellectual, creative, emotional, etc.).

6. Correctional: in the game, the process of making changes in the student's personality structure occurs naturally.

7. Interethnic communication: the game allows the student to assimilate universal values, culture of representatives of different nationalities.

8. Socialization: the game is one of the best inclusions of the student in the system of social relations.

The pedagogical value of the game, in our opinion, lies in the fact that it is the strongest motivational factor, since the child is guided by personal attitudes and motives.

Gaming technologies contribute to the actualization of various motives of educational activities and, above all, such as:

- motives of communication;
- moral motives;
- cognitive motives.

Motivation of game activity is provided by its voluntariness, choice opportunities and elements of competition, satisfaction of needs, self-affirmation, self-realization.

One of the urgent problems of modern methods of teaching foreign languages is the organization of teaching children of different ages using game technologies. The urgency of this problem is caused by a number of factors. First, the intensification of the educational process poses the task of finding means of maintaining students' interest in the material being studied and activating their activities throughout the lesson. Educational games are an effective means of solving this problem. Secondly, one of the most important problems

of teaching a foreign language is the teaching of oral speech, which creates conditions for the disclosure of the communicative function of the language and allows you to bring the learning process closer to the conditions of real learning, which increases the motivation for learning a foreign language. The involvement of students in oral communication can be successfully carried out in the process of game activities.

We propose to classify the games used in foreign language lessons (FL) into two main groups:

1. Didactic games, which include grammatical, lexical, phonetic and spelling games that contribute to the formation of speech skills in students. Unlike games in general, a didactic game has an essential feature - a clearly defined learning goal and a corresponding result, which can be substantiated, explicitly singled out and characterized by an educational and cognitive orientation. In and through the didactic game, the gamers have to learn something. The didactic game is characterized by the following:

- communication with a specific educational goal;
- the ability to repeat, interrupt or start over at any time;
- openness, i.e. the end of the game is not precisely defined;
- adherence to explicit rules that can be changed by gamers;
- satisfaction from participation, absence of "consequences" for the gamers (this activity should not be evaluated in any way).

In our opinion, the fundamental difference between didactic games and exercises and tasks is that:

First, the game does not have a predetermined pattern of behavior, and the participant himself chooses a possible version

of speech interaction and evaluates the result of its implementation. The only limiting factor for the content and form of the game is educational material (lesson topic, goal, planned results).

Secondly, the game is usually adversarial, competitive. The student, entering into relationships with partners in the game, evaluates his strengths not only in comparison with other gamers. The game allows him to objectively assess his capabilities.

Thirdly, in the game, schoolchildren learn interpersonal and group communication, learn to choose the optimal means of solving (linguistic and non-linguistic) conflict situations. In the game, the ability is formed to correlate their actions with the actions of other gamers, that is, to cooperate.

Martinson divides didactic games used in foreign language classes into two large groups: 1) "games with language material" and 2) "games in language" [4]. The first correspond to classes aimed at systematizing language material. At the same time, much attention is paid to the knowledge of grammar rules. Therefore, such games are well suited for training at the beginning, but also for training individual structures at an advanced stage. Games with language material can be fully programmed and therefore controlled. Wagner calls such games "transformed exercises", which are not playful in nature, but are transformed into games only due to the presence of a competitive element.

The author notes that "the closed nature of games, the leading role of the teacher, become the reason for the unsuitability of games of this kind for lessons in conversational practice" [5]. But this does not mean that they cannot be successfully applied for certain purposes.

Games with linguistic material are introduced formally for educational purposes and serve both to consolidate structures and

grammatical rules, and to automate certain speech skills. The purpose of the game and its course can be easily planned in advance and explained unambiguously. They are suitable for teaching purposes in traditional pursuits. Games of this kind contribute to the systematization of foreign language material in a simple game scheme: bingo lotto, games in pairs, board games, crosswords, etc. Most often, these games are introduced to train spelling or vocabulary systematization.

Didactic games "in the language" are used primarily to consolidate the skills of listening, reading, speaking and writing. The didactic communicative game presupposes such an organization of joint communicative activity of the teacher and students, during which the features of the speech behavior of schoolchildren are simultaneously manifested and foreign language communication skills are formed.

2. Creative, role-playing games are one of the ways to learn foreign languages. Concepts such as role-playing, simulation, drama, and acting are often used interchangeably, but in reality, they have different meanings. The difference between role game and simulation lies in the authenticity of the roles played by the students. In the simulation, students play their natural role, in other words, the role they game in real life (for example, the role of a buyer or booking transport tickets). In role-playing, students play a role that they do not game in real life (for example, the prime minister or rock star). The role-playing game can be considered as one of the components or elements of the simulation. Thus, in a role-playing game, participants assign the roles that they game in the scenario. The simulation focuses on the interaction of one role with other roles, rather than on playing out individual roles. Either way, role game

prepares students for social interaction in a different social and cultural context.

Thus, role game is a highly flexible learning activity with a wide range of possibilities for variety and imagination. In role-playing games, various communication techniques are widely used, thereby developing fluency in the language, interaction in the classroom and increasing motivation. Role-game improves the speaking skills of students in any situation, because almost all the learning time in the role-game is devoted to speech practice, while not only the speaker, but also the listener is as active as possible, since he must understand and remember the partner's remark, correlate it with the game situation, determine how relevant it is to the situation and the task of communication and respond correctly to it. For shy students, role game helps by providing a mask with which students with communication difficulties are relieved. Plus, it's fun, and most students will agree that fun leads to better learning.

In turn, role-playing games can be classified as follows:

1. Short-term role-playing game, which is the simplest and fastest type of game, lasting from 10 to 30 minutes. It can be based on text or dialogue. An example of this game can be presented in the form of an interview. Students are divided into pairs, after which they are given pictures depicting various problem situations (environmental pollution, deforestation, lack of food in zoos). One of the students takes on the role of the interviewer, the other the role of the respondent. The task is to describe the problem and propose a solution. The game component is that experts are also appointed among the students, whose task is to formulate a criterion for assessing and subsequently evaluate all the speakers and point out the mistakes made. In the course of

this game, there is a high motivation and desire of students to show themselves, because one of the assessment criteria can be artistry.

2. A full-fledged role game in which students are provided with a description of the situation and their roles. The duration of this type of games, on average, takes one or two lessons. As an example, consider verbal role-playing games. This archetype of games occurs through the verbal interaction of participants describing the actions of their game characters, and a mentor, in the role of which a teacher can act, describing the realities of the game world. One of the most famous board word games is Mafia. Role-playing game

"Mafia" is very popular all over the world, and allows you to game it, both in class and in extracurricular activities using the Internet. Pupils, paying attention to the course of the game, begin to speak spontaneously. Their goal is to convince the rest of the gamers that this or that participant is the mafia / doctor / sheriff. The use of this game within the framework of the lesson helps students develop their communicative competence, teaches them to defend their point of view, convince and encourages them to take initiative.

3. Long-term role-playing games, is a more complex type of games lasting from a series of sessions or more. When preparing long-term role-playing games, the teacher should provide students with handouts, familiarize students with the game setting through a Case Study, and provide students with a clear definition of the game situation. In this archetype of games, students are given the opportunity to create their own game character. Students can choose gender, race, age, profession, depending on the proposed game. An example of these games is the Dungeons and Dragons series, a tabletop role-

playing game. In D&D, students try on the role of fantasy heroes with their own skills and characteristics. The teacher takes on the role of a mentor who creates and describes an adventure in which the heroes of the students take part, setting goals for them to fulfill and giving rewards for motivation. The purpose of this game is to get students to work together, solving problems and puzzles that the teacher puts before them in the process of studying the world of the game. Thus, allowing to achieve the main goal - the development of communicative competence.

The characters created by students during this game can be used in subsequent lessons, giving students the opportunity to be who they want, thereby turning monotonous stories about themselves into fascinating stories.

4. Computer role-playing games. In our time, it is difficult to imagine a person unfamiliar with computer role-playing games. Moreover, in the 21st century, a child spends most of his free time at the computer. It is computer games that can motivate a student studying a foreign language and game a huge role in his self-development. For those teachers whose students have free Internet access, role-playing games can be a good choice. These games give interested students the opportunity to establish direct contact with people from all over the world who have common interests but who need to use English to communicate, thus highlighting the value of language learning beyond school grades. Most computer role-playing games have the ability to train both listening and reading skills. The games have a lot of stories, dialogues, screensavers, presented in a foreign language.

Of course, it is difficult to use a computer role-playing game to learn

grammar, but an experienced teacher is quite capable of creating an algorithm for training exercises.

An example of a computer role-playing game is Minecraft. This game is made in the style of a sandbox, the participants of which can build and survive, cooperating with other gamers.

Computer role-playing games, with the right approach, can help students learn not only a foreign language, but history, geography and other subjects, as well as contribute to the formation of the student's meta-subject skills.

However, when using computer games, it is important to follow the rules that help preserve the health and eyesight of students, as well as not let a good hobby take them away from reality.

Thus, gaming technology occupies an important place in the educational process. A wide variety of role-playing games can be used in any part of the curriculum. At the same time, they are a very useful tool that makes learning a foreign language interesting and memorable. Role-playing games provide a positive emotional state of students and a communicative focus of the lesson. Game activity is the most attractive for schoolchildren, which affects the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language. Games have a positive effect on the formation of students' cognitive interests, contribute to the conscious mastering of a foreign language. They contribute to the development of such qualities as independence, initiative, the ability to work in a team. Students actively, enthusiastically work, help each other, listen attentively to their comrades, and the teacher only controls their learning activities.

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